

LiDAR Point Cloud Virtual Reality Visual Evaluation Through Structural Similarity Index Measure and Edge Metric Similarity

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Abstract. VR has become one of the most reliable simulation techniques due to the practicality of human-subject research. Meanwhile, VR simulation technology aims to achieve the best photorealistic environment for the best immersive experience. However, wayfinding VR simulation with a point cloud environment must be evaluated to determine its feasibility in identifying wayfinding variables. Therefore, this study will analyse the visual quality of point cloud presentation in VR using near and far point observation, SSIM (Structural Similarity Index Measure), edge similarity, Frame Per Second (FPS), and flicker visibility. Various VR point cloud densities were assessed against ground truth images. The result indicated that the higher the density, the better the visual quality for the optimum VR simulation. Nonetheless, a 10 million point cloud density is sufficient for VR simulation, even though 20 million provides a denser and more detailed point representation.

BoK Concepts. [CV4-7] Virtual and immersive environments, [TA14-2-1-1] Point clouds, [GC2] Spatial simulation modelling

Keywords. point cloud, SSIM, virtual reality, wayfinding, edge canny detection

1 Introduction

Wayfinding simulation using Virtual Reality (VR) has recently been used more frequently in various studies due to its ability to cater to the dynamic of human subject research (Dong et al., 2022). VR wayfinding studies have introduced various digital environments, which are projected to bring a photorealistic environment into the simulation. LiDAR Point cloud can provide a photorealistic environment because it can scan directly from the real environment. Nonetheless, VR simulation using a point cloud is quite uncommon. Many have begun

to explore the merging and compatibility of point cloud and VR visualisation in various scenarios (Michalas et al., 2024; Yasar et al., 2024). However, discussions related to its VR visualisation feasibility are still rarely explored. Therefore, this study aims to provide an approach to evaluate the visual fidelity of a point cloud environment for VR wayfinding simulation.

2 Methodology

This study examines the visual clarity of point cloud visualised in VR using Unreal Engine 5 (UE5) and Quest 2 Head Mounted Device (HMD). The experiment tested a digital environment of a faculty building with an approximate floor area of 463 m² and a captured volume of approximately 858 m³, based on volume calculation tools in CloudCompare. The spatial data was acquired using a Zeb Vision LiDAR scanner and processed in Faro Connect, CloudCompare, and Google Colab.

The research involves four main stages: data collection, pre-processing, simulation, analysis and statistical evaluation (figure 1). After scanning, the point cloud representation undergoes .slam data processing, noise reduction, integration between segments, and point density reduction. The density reduction produces six different densities, from 500 thousand to 20 million, to overview the impact of point density on the visual quality in VR. The lowest point density is 500 thousand because it is the most stable for VR visualisation on low-spec computers or laptops.

During the simulation, the process is recorded and captured. The captured images are then processed using Canny Edge detection to produce the edge structure through noise reduction, gradient calculation, non-maximum suppression, double thresholding, and edge tracking (Tasneem and Afroze, 2019). The processed image was then further evaluated using the Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) and Edge similarity by comparing the VR point cloud image with the actual

Figure 1. Research method workflow

picture image that serves as the ground truth. SSIM evaluates luminance, contrast, and structure to assess visual fidelity (Wang et al., 2004; Wang and Bovik, 2002). In the similarity assessment process, the precisions are computed by comparing the pixels of the edge maps (point cloud and real picture edge image). The score indicated a fraction of identical pixels, showing the measurement of edge interaction.

2.1 Data and Software Availability

Point cloud data presented in this study is openly available under a permissive CC-BY-SA 4.0 licence with DOI: 10.4121/1ccabad8-d891-4dd4-90e7-49d5e329f980. The files can also be accessed through the following [link](#).

3 Results and Discussion

Different densities of points in VR visualisation significantly affect how the points are presented in the HMD. The fewer the points, the coarser the edges are

created by the points. On the contrary, the denser the points, the smoother the surface will be. By default, UE5 would fill the gap created in the sparse point cloud by creating bigger points, as seen in the 500-thousand-point image (Figure 2). Furthermore, as we observe in detail in Figure 3, it is noticeable that the closer our view to the surrounding space, the greater the voids between the points, especially with low-density point cloud representation, such as 500 thousand points to 1 million points. Nonetheless, the voids are getting smaller along with the density increase. On the other hand, the voids in the far view are relatively smaller and gradually diminish, beginning at 10 million points.

The images are processed using Canny Edge detection to retrieve their edge feature and then compared to the real environment image using SSIM and Edge Similarity (%) metric (figure 4). SSIM evaluates the structural information created from the image luminance and contrast, the evaluation metric of which ranges from -1 to 1. Score 1 means that the image has perfect structural similarity. A zero (0) score means that it has no structural

Figure 2. VR visualisation of different point cloud density

Figure 3. VR visualisation of near and far point scarcity in different point cloud density

similarity. A negative value would mean that the images have dissimilar structures.

SSIM score results of the tested images range from 0.4237 to 0.4647, indicating low to moderate structural similarity. This indicated that the higher point cloud densities are well identified while the lower ones are generally still identifiable, although not as clear. Additionally, the low result signifies that the structural image detail between VR visualised point clouds compared to the real environment photo differs significantly.

The Edge Similarity percentage analysis result showed a steady trend ranging from 87.32 to 88.95 % (Table 1). The data are collected by comparing the extracted edges of the VR point cloud image and the actual environment image. The result showed that despite the differences in density, all possess clear edges to help identify a clear border.

In addition to the SSIM and edge similarity metric, this study observes each point density's average Frame Per Second (FPS) during the VR simulation to evaluate the performance and real-time rendering capability. The result showed a significant decline in FPS from 98 (500 thousand) to 59 (1 million). After that, the FPS remains steady at 59 and 56 at the rest of the points (Table 1).

Furthermore, during the simulation, some visible flickering begins from 10 million to 20 million (Table 1). Nonetheless, in 10 million, the flickering only appears mildly, covering only small areas and lasting a short period. While severe flickering has broader areas and longer periods.

Figure 4. Result of pre-processed image using Canny Edge detection on various VR point cloud density and ground truth image

Table 1. SSIM and Edge similarity score across density

No	Number of Points (Density)	SSIM	Edge Similarity (%)	FPS	Visible Point Flicker
1	500 Thousand	0.4237	87.32	98	no
2	1 million	0.4260	87.14	59	no
3	5 million	0.4154	86.20	59	no
4	10 million	0.4491	88.14	56	mild
5	15 million	0.4516	88.13	56	severe
6	20 million	0.4647	88.95	56	severe

4 Conclusion

The evaluation considers several aspects and metrics: point scarcity, visual clarity in close and far view, SSIM metric, edge similarity, FPS, and flicker visibility. The result showed 10 million points as the lowest densities for appropriate visual fidelity due to its ability to provide sufficient visual quality and stable performance. Although 5 million points maintained high FPS with no visible flicker, the SSIM and edge similarity scores indicated insufficient structural clarity for wayfinding tasks, especially in close-up views. Meanwhile, 20 million points have the best visual quality, but at the cost of increased computational demand and visible flickering. Therefore, balancing user experience with visual clarity is crucial for effective VR wayfinding tasks.

Future research should address technology challenges before involving human participants to investigate depth perception, spatial awareness, and task performance in dense point cloud VR environments. These challenges include optimising large-scale point cloud handling within VR headsets, which could be solved through caching strategies required for an adaptive and continuous level of detail of the point cloud. Furthermore, finding a balance between point cloud and Gaussian splatting would be beneficial in providing a photorealistic VR environment. Special attention should also be directed toward modelling various transitional spaces, as these play a crucial role in wayfinding dynamics.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have not used Generative AI tools to prepare this manuscript. Specifically, the AI tools were utilized for language editing and improving grammar and sentence structure but not for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

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References

- Dong, W., Qin, T., Yang, T., Liao, H., Liu, B., Meng, L., and Liu, Y.: Wayfinding Behavior and Spatial Knowledge Acquisition: Are They the Same in Virtual Reality and in Real-World Environments?, *Ann. Am. Assoc. Geogr.*, 112, 226–246, <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2021.1894088>, 2022.
- Michalas, M., de Niet, E. C. J., Martinez, J., Wang, Z., and Manden, B.: Explorative Point Cloud Virtual Reality: Immersive Visual Insight, 2024.
- Tasneem, T. and Afroze, Z.: A New Method of Improving Performance of Canny Edge Detection, in: 2019 2nd International Conference on Innovation in Engineering and Technology (ICIET), 2019 2nd International Conference on Innovation in Engineering and Technology (ICIET), 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIET48527.2019.9290676>, 2019.
- Wang, Z. and Bovik, A. C.: A universal image quality index, *IEEE Signal Process. Lett.*, 9, 81–84, <https://doi.org/10.1109/97.995823>, 2002.
- Wang, Z., Bovik, A. C., Sheikh, H. R., and Simoncelli, E. P.: Image quality assessment: from error visibility to structural similarity, *IEEE Trans. Image Process.*, 13, 600–612, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIP.2003.819861>, 2004.
- Yasar, A. M., Voûte, R., and Verbree, E.: Direct Use of Indoor Point Clouds for Path Planning and Navigation Exploration in Emergency Situations, *Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spat. Inf. Sci.*, XLVIII-4-W11-2024, 175–181, <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLVIII-4-W11-2024-175-2024>, 2024.